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Monitoring of Corrosion Process in Structural Adhesive using Smart Materials

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Abstract

The use of structural adhesives, such as epoxy, for the strengthening and repair of civil infrastructure is gaining popularity in the engineering community. Of particular concern to the viability of intervention measure is the degradation of strength and durability of the epoxy over time, especially when exposed to aggressive environments. Monitoring the corrosion process of epoxy is thus essential to ensure safety of the host structure. In this paper, the electromechanical impedance (EMI) technique that employs a smart piezoelectric transducer is used to monitor the degradation process of commercially available epoxy when exposed to corrosive environments. Standard epoxy coupons with surface bonded piezoelectric transducer are prepared and then immersed in either acidic or saline conditions in the laboratory. Experimental results show that the change in frequency of resonance peaks in the admittance signatures versus the frequency spectrum is a good indicator of the corrosion process. This study proves that the EMI technique is effective in characterising the severity of corrosion inflicted on the epoxy. The capability of the EMI technique in providing autonomous, real-time, remote monitoring with quick response using non-intrusive active sensors could potentially replace its conventional counterparts.

1. Introduction

The use of structural adhesives for repair and strengthening of structure are gaining popularity in the aerospace, mechanical and civil engineering disciplines due to their excellent mechanical and physical properties. Adhesive connections possess various advantages such as the ease of joining different materials and components of complicated forms within short period of time.

In the early years, application of structural adhesives in civil engineering has been focusing on bridge construction, especially for connections between bridge decks and steels girders (Messler 2004).

The use of structural adhesive in the civil engineering discipline has thus far been impeded by the harsh environmental conditions. In depth studies into the influences of environmental factors on the performance of the adhesive joints is necessary, before real life application in the industry and potential replacement of conventional methods of connections such as bolting is possible.

The performance of structural adhesives can often be degraded by hostile environment such as temperature, moisture, salt, acidity. The severity of degradation can be aggravated with a combination of these conditions.

If epoxy-based adhesives is in contact with water, their mechanical performance is altered by the absorption of water into the polymer chains. In addition to weakening the physical and chemical properties of the structural adhesive, the presence of moisture will also degrade the strength of the interfacial bonding between the adhesive and the adherend (Banea and da Silva 2009). For metallic adherend, water will diffuse into the joint through the adhesive. The interface between the adhesive

and adherend will also be intruded by the water with time. In general, the weakening of a joint is predominantly caused by the degradation of the interface between the adhesive and adherend rather than the weakening of the adhesive.

Lapique and Redford (2002) conducted an ageing test on commercially available structural adhesive, Araldite 2014 exposed to water vapour over 36 days in a controlled environment at 40°C. The experiment showed that the adhesive was softened in the presence of moisture. The elastic modulus reduced and the plastic deformation increased correspondingly.

Prolongo and Urena (2007) found that an epoxy-aluminium joint immersed in a saline environment experienced degradation with time. It was also discovered that the durability of the adhesive joints under such environment can be considerably enhanced with the provision of appropriate surface treatments.

Recently, Wong (2017) investigated the feasibility of using the electromechanical impedance (EMI) technique for detecting the wall thickness reduction in pipeline due to corrosion. It was found that the resonance frequency range shifted when the thickness of the wall was reduced. Talakokula et al. (2014) studied the corrosion process of steel reinforcing bars using the EMI technique. The experimental results indicated that the equivalent structural parameters derived from the mechanical impedance of the steel structure were effective in detecting and quantifying the corrosion process.

Thus far, limited study has been conducted on the application of EMI technique on structural adhesive. In this paper, a novel study is presented, in which the feasibility of adopting the smart piezoelectric (PZT) based EMI technique in monitoring the corrosion process of structural adhesives is investigated. The EMI technique possesses various advantages over other conventional health monitoring techniques as the PZT transducers are low cost, non-intrusive, respond rapidly, adaptable to large scale application, with autonomous, real-time and remote monitoring capability. The PZT patches can be installed at various locations on critical structural members in order to monitor local damage or overall structural integrity.

The principal of application of the EMI technique (Lim and Soh 2011) is the piezoelectric effect, in which the PZT is capable of converting electrical energy to mechanical energy and vice versa. When an alternating voltage of varying frequency is applied across the poling direction of a PZT transducer that is mechanically attached to a host structure, the transducer can be mechanically excited (known as the converse effect of piezoelectricity) and subsequently actuates the attached host structure. At the same time, the vibratory response of the host structure will interact with the PZT transducer, thus altering the corresponding electric current.

The current, in the form of complex electrical admittance, can be measured by an impedance analyser. Subsequent alterations in the vibratory behaviour of the host structure as a result of damage (Lim and Soh 2014), change in stress, boundary condition or in mechanical properties (Lim et al. 2016; Kong and Song 2017) can therefore be reflected in the admittance signatures.

2. Experimental study

2.1 Experimental Setup

In this study, commercially available two-part thermosetting epoxy, Sikadur 30 (Sika 2014), was used for the corrosion tests. The liquid epoxy was first mixed and placed into standard “dog bone” shape mould according to the British Standard (BS EN, 1996). Four identical epoxy coupon were produced. They were allowed to fully cure at a constant room temperature of 24°C for two weeks. One PZT patch, dimensioned 10mm x 10mm x 0.3mm, was surface bonded at the centre of the epoxy coupon. A typical “dog bone” coupon specimen is shown in Figure 1(a).

An impedance analyser (Hioki IM3570) was used to apply an alternating voltage (5V) across the PZT transducer and to also simultaneously record its electrical admittance as shown in Figure 1(b).

The frequency range considered was 5 kHz – 900 kHz, while the electrical signatures were first acquired at a healthy or undamaged stage. The specimens were then subjected to various corrosive environments as summarised in Table 1. Note that the specimens were not fully immersed into the respective solution in order to avoid damaging the PZT patch. Instead, sponges were used to wrap around the specimens which were then dipped into the solution, so that the solution was in contact with the specimens but not the PZT patches. Specimen Ctrl serves as control, which is placed alongside other specimens inside the same laboratory with controlled temperature (24°C) throughout the period of monitoring.

The admittance signatures were acquired once per day for 11 days. Each time before the signature acquisition started, the specimens were removed from the solution and placed on a dry cloth for 10-15 minutes. This ensured the signatures are acquired under the same condition.

Figure 1. Experimental setup for EMI based corrosion monitoring of epoxy.

Table 1: Summary of test specimens under various corrosive environment

Specimen Label	Environment
Ctrl	Control
Wtr	Water
NaCl	Sodium chloride of 10% concentration
H2SO4	Sulphuric acid of 10% concentration

2.2 Admittance Signatures at Healthy Stage

The admittance signatures acquired from the PZT surface bonded on Specimen Ctrl is depicted in Figure 2. The result shows a wide frequency range from 0 – 900 kHz which reflects several large peaks representing the PZT patch resonances. Figure 2(b), on the other hand, offers a magnified view of the first 70 kHz which is characterised by densely spaced structural peaks, representing the resonances of the epoxy coupon. These peaks are a useful indicator of the vibratory behaviour of the host structure (Lim et al. 2006), which will be altered when subjected to structural changes such as corrosion.

2.3 Repeatability of signatures – Control Specimen

Referring again to Figure 2, it can be shown that the repeatability of signatures on Specimen Ctrl can be satisfactorily high throughout the period of monitoring, as shown from the overlapping of signatures throughout the period of monitoring. This indicates that no sign of degradation is shown on this specimen, which is placed inside the laboratory throughout the period of monitoring. In

other words, any changes in signatures shown on other specimens would be caused by the corrosion process.

Figure 2. Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from PZT patch surface bonded on Specimen Ctrl
(a) 0 – 900 kHz (b) – 70 kHz

2.4 Unprotected PZT Patch in 10% Sulphuric Acid

Despite the fact that the PZT patches are not fully immersed into the solution, they are unprotected and hence the acid caused considerable damage to the PZT patch on Specimen H₂SO₄. This can be reflected from Figure 3, where the signatures acquired after the specimen had been exposed to the corrosive acid for one day deviate significantly from the healthy stage, indicating that the PZT patch itself is damaged. Signs of corrosion can be visually observed on the PZT patch, confirming the changes on the electrical signatures. This observation is similar to the study reported by Yang, Lim and Soh (2008).

Figure 3. Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from PZT patch surface bonded on Specimen H2SO4 (without protection)

This is considered as a premature failure and it is undesirable as the PZT patch failed to perform after the first day of monitoring. The test was thus repeated with the PZT patch being protected by applying 2 layers of quick set epoxy over the surface before it was placed in the corrosive environment.

3. Monitoring of Corrosion Process

To monitor the process of corrosion, peaks representing the host structural resonances in the lower frequency range (<70 kHz) were adopted. Figure 4 shows a plot of admittance signatures within a selected frequency range (20 – 40 kHz) for Specimen H2SO4 throughout the period of monitoring. The signatures change continuously throughout that period but the shape of the curve remains essentially the same.

Magnifying the frequency range of 23 – 26 kHz shows one typical structural resonance peak within the lower range spectrum. It is observed that there is an abrupt decrease in resonance frequency (leftward movement) and magnitude after one day. The peak continuously moves to the left at a reduced rate thereafter. Ignoring the change in magnitude, which is less representative of damage (Lim, Bhalla and Soh 2006), the decrease in resonance frequency reflects a reduction in stiffness of the host structure. This observation is in line with the physical corrosion process, where the stiffness of the coupon is expected to reduce when it is attacked by the acid.

The corresponding changes in resonance frequency across the entire period of this particular peak is schematically summarised in Figure 5. Observing the gradual reduction in resonance frequency, it can be confidently concluded that the change in resonance frequency is a good indicator of the corrosion process. On the other hand, observing the gradient of the curve, it can be shown that the corrosion process is significant in the first day and is reduced after 3 days. Note that a similar conclusion can be drawn from other resonance peaks within the first 70 kHz.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Conductance signatures versus frequency acquired from PZT patch surface bonded on Specimen H2SO4
 (a) 20 – 40 kHz (b) 23 – 26 kHz

Figure 5. Resonance frequency acquired from PZT patch surface bonded on Specimen H2SO4

Similar observation can be found from Specimen NaCl, which is exposed to 10% sodium chloride, as presented in Figure 6. In this case, a resonance peak occurring at 50.65 kHz is selected as damage indicator. In this case, however, the total reduction in resonance frequency across 11 days is 0.15 kHz, in comparison to a total of 0.35 kHz in Specimen H2SO4. This clearly reflects the fact that the corrosion inflicted on Specimen H2SO4, which is exposed to acidic solution, is much more severe than Specimen NaCl which is exposed to saline solution.

Figure 6. Resonance frequency acquired from PZT patch surface bonded on Specimen NaCl

Finally, observation is also made on Specimen Wtr, which is exposed to tap water. In this case no significant change in resonance frequency is observed, apart from some minor variations in magnitude. This indicates that water is not corrosive and has not caused significant reduction in stiffness of the host structure in such a short term of exposure. However, future study may focus on longer term monitoring to observe any possible changes with time.

4. Conclusion

This paper investigates the feasibility of employing the PZT based EMI technique in monitoring the corrosion process of epoxy. Experimental results show that the changes in electrical admittance acquired can be correlated to the corrosion process. The reduction of resonance frequency of selected structural peaks is found to reflect the stiffness reduction process of the host structure as corrosion takes place. The severity of corrosion on specimen exposed to acid in comparison to sodium chloride is also reflected from the extent of alteration of the resonance frequency, which shows the robustness of the proposed technique in detecting and characterising the corrosion process. Future studies can focus on developing parametric or statistical quantification approaches to monitor the actual severity of the corrosion process. The capability of the EMI technique in providing autonomous, real-time, remote monitoring with quick response using non-intrusive active sensors could potentially replace its conventional counterparts.

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